

Class Imbalance in Credit Card Fraud Detection: A Comparative Study of CatBoost and XGBoost

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Abstract

Despite extensive research on class imbalance in financial fraud detection, comparative analyses of CatBoost and algorithm-level class balancing methods remain limited, with PR-AUC less frequently reported. The current study compares CatBoost, XGBoost, and LightGBM on the IEEE-CIS credit card fraud (CCF) dataset, investigating data-level (ROS, RUS, SMOTE) and algorithm-level (CSL) methods for handling class imbalance, evaluated on PR-AUC, with validation on secondary datasets (ULB and PaySim). Across all datasets, PR-AUC results show that CatBoost consistently outperformed LightGBM and XGBoost at baseline and after feature engineering and hyperparameter optimization, with CSL consistently achieving the strongest class-balancing results for CatBoost and XGBoost. The strongest overall performing model on IEEE-CIS was CatBoost with CSL (PR-AUC of 0.75 and ROC-AUC of 0.96), outperforming the best XGBoost (PR-AUC of 0.67 and ROC-AUC of 0.93) and LightGBM (PR-AUC of 0.68 and ROC-AUC of 0.93) configurations, likely due to its native handling of categorical features and ordered boosting, which reduce target leakage and overfitting. These findings suggest that CatBoost, particularly when combined with CSL, can provide a robust and effective approach for CCF detection under severe class imbalance, thereby offering practical insight for future CCF research.

Keywords: Credit card fraud, class imbalance, CatBoost, XGBoost, LightGBM, TreeSHAP, SMOTE, RUS, ROS, CSL

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

With the rapid growth of online transactions, fraudulent activities are escalating, creating a pressing need for more accurate fraud detection solutions. Credit card fraud (CCF) datasets are characterized by having significant class imbalance, which can lead the model to have bias towards the majority class and generalize poorly on the minority class. As a result, models may fail to detect fraud, while also increase false alarms.

Several factors can be considered to mitigate the effects of class imbalance, including model selection, evaluation metrics, and data balancing techniques.

1.2 Model Selection

Model selection plays a crucial role in addressing class imbalance, while there isn't a one-size-fits-all model, some models are inherently more suitable for imbalanced tabular datasets.

Tree-based gradient boosting models such as XGBoost, CatBoost, and LightGBM (hereafter referred to as boosting models) have shown strong performance in CCF detection. They are well-suited for tabular data and can handle class imbalance effectively (Shwartz-Ziv and Armon, 2022), while also being robust to outliers (Friedman, 2001). In addition, these models can handle high percentage of missing values without requiring imputation or data removal (Rusdah and Murfi, 2020), a crucial advantage given that CCF datasets can contain up to 45% missing values (e.g., IEEE-CIS dataset (IEEE Computational Intelligence Society and Vesta Corporation, 2019)). When compared with traditional models (e.g., logistic regression (LR) and support vector machine (SVM)), studies indicate that boosting models can capture complex patterns more efficiently (Leevy et al., 2023; Mienye and Sun, 2023). And when compared to deep neural networks (DNNs), boosting models have fewer and more interpretable hyperparameters

(Rusdah and Murfi, 2020), require less computational power, faster model updates, and easier adaptation after deployment (Shwartz-Ziv and Armon, 2022), making them efficient for real-world CCF systems, such as banks, where fraud tactics evolve rapidly to catch up with increased security, requiring frequent model updates.

Among boosting models, XGBoost is the most widely adopted in CCF detection. It implements an advanced gradient boosting framework, where decision trees are built sequentially and each tree corrects the errors of the previous one (Chen, 2016). XGBoost is also robust to overfitting due to its regularization terms, which control tree depth and leaf weight (Rusdah and Murfi, 2020). Similarly, CatBoost combines many trees and corrects the mistakes of the previous ones (Prokhorenkova et al., 2018). However, it is built to handle categorical features natively without the need for encoding by converting categories into numerical values using target statistics with ordered boosting which helps avoid target leakage overfitting (Prokhorenkova et al., 2018). CatBoost is specifically designed to handle categorical features (Prokhorenkova et al., 2018), commonly present in CCF datasets (e.g., address, email). Despite this, CatBoost remains less explored in CCF detection, especially as a standalone.

1.3 Class Balancing Methods

Class imbalance is commonly addressed at the data and algorithm levels.

1.3.1 Data-Level Approach

Data-level methods are the most widely applied in research to handle class imbalance. They fix the imbalance by changing the distribution of the data, either by oversampling, undersampling, or both (Kim and Song, 2025). In oversampling, the size of the minority class increases either by duplicating samples in a method called Random Oversampling (ROS), or by generating new synthetic samples by interpolating between existing minority points in a method called Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) (Kim and Song, 2025). Undersampling works on reducing the size of the majority class by randomly dropping samples from the majority class, with Random Undersampling (RUS) being the most common (Kim and Song, 2025).

Data-level methods are relatively simple to apply but come with limitations. Oversampling can increase the risk of overfitting, as duplicating samples can lead the model to memorize patterns instead of generalizing (He and Garcia, 2009). Moreover, oversampling using SMOTE can create unrealistic samples as they interpolate blindly and increase noise (He and Garcia, 2009). Conversely, undersampling can miss important instances while removing samples (Kim

and Song, 2025; Prabha and Priscilla, 2024). Researchers acknowledge these limitations by combining data-level methods with algorithm-level (Makki et al., 2019; Malik et al., 2022), or by relying on algorithm-level methods alone (Hashemi et al., 2022; Priscilla and Prabha, 2021; Wang et al., 2025).

1.3.2 Algorithm-Level Approach

An alternate method is to deal with imbalanced data at the algorithm level through adjusting the way the model learns, without manipulating the data (Kim and Song, 2025; He and Garcia, 2009). Algorithm-level approaches include class-sensitive learning (CSL) techniques such as class weighting and custom loss functions. In class weighting and focal loss the model assigns higher error cost to misclassifying the minority class, this helps reshape the learning objective by penalizing false negatives more heavily, encouraging the model to focus on rare cases (e.g., fraud) during training. As a result, the model becomes more sensitive to minority-class, improving recall at the potential cost of increased false positives (He and Garcia, 2009; Kim and Song, 2025). Nonetheless, only few CCF detection studies utilize algorithm-level approaches for imbalanced data (e.g., (Hashemi et al., 2022; Prabha and Priscilla, 2023; Wang et al., 2025)).

1.4 Evaluation Metrics

Evaluation metrics reflecting minority class are necessary for reliable performance assessment in imbalanced data. Receiver Operating Characteristic Area Under the Curve (ROC-AUC) is a frequently used metric in CCF detection (Tayebi and El Kafhali, 2025; Mim et al., 2024; Nguyen et al., 2022; Nti and Somanathan, 2022). The literature indicates that when class imbalance is severe ROC-AUC can give optimistic results due to weighting true positives and true negatives equally (Davis and Goadrich, 2006; Saito and Rehmsmeier, 2015).

On the other hand, studies show that Precision–Recall Area Under the Curve (PR-AUC) is more sensitive to the minority class (Davis and Goadrich, 2006; Saito and Rehmsmeier, 2015; Leevy et al., 2023; Hashemi et al., 2022; Alamri and Ykhlef, 2024). This is because PR-AUC incorporates precision, directly penalizing false positives (Bekkar et al., 2013), thus making it sensitive to minority-class performance, whereas ROC-AUC includes true negatives from the majority class (Davis and Goadrich, 2006), which can inflate the score under severe class imbalance masking poor performance. Despite this only a few studies incorporated PR-AUC in CCF detection, while the majority reported ROC-AUC.

1.5 Research Questions

Overall, boosting models proved effective in CCF detection, however, CatBoost remains less frequently applied as a standalone model. Furthermore, algorithm-level class balancing approaches received less attention despite their advantage of handling class imbalance without altering data distribution. Finally, PR-AUC remains less commonly used for model evaluation even though it provides more informative assessment of minority-class performance in the presence of severe class imbalance.

Therefore, this study aims to:

- Compare CatBoost’s performance with XGBoost and LightGBM using PR-AUC on the IEEE-CIS CCF dataset before and after applying class balancing methods.
- Examine the impact of algorithm-level class balancing method (CSL) compared to data-level methods (SMOTE, RUS, ROS) in CCF detection.
- Investigate the impact of evaluation metric choice (PR-AUC vs. ROC-AUC) on model performance under severe class imbalance.
- Assess the robustness of IEEE-CIS findings on additional real and synthetic datasets.

1.6 Contributions

The contributions of this study are as follows:

- A PR-AUC–based comparative analysis of CatBoost, XGBoost, and LightGBM on imbalanced CCF datasets.
- A comparative evaluation of algorithm-level class balancing methods (CSL) and data-level approaches (SMOTE, RUS, ROS) in boosting models.
- Robustness evaluation of model and class-balancing method rankings across multiple datasets.
- An explainable AI (XAI) analysis using TreeSHAP to identify key features influencing fraud predictions.
- An empirical analysis of how PR-AUC versus ROC-AUC affect interpretation of model performance under severe class imbalance.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Overview

The purpose of this report is to address the class imbalance challenge in CCF datasets by comparing boosting algorithms and imbalance handling methods. Table 2.1 summarizes recent studies on CCF detection, focusing on primary models, evaluation metrics, and class balancing methods.

2.2 Model Selection

Traditional classifiers are applied in CCF detection often in combination with boosting models. The results consistently show that traditional algorithms performance improves when boosting models are added. Ileberi et al. (2021) evaluated a range of classifiers including SVM, LR, decision trees (DT), random forest (RF), extra tree (ET), and XGBoost. Their findings showed that applying AdaBoost enhanced the performance of all models, with XGBoost–AdaBoost combination emerging as one of the top performers. Similarly, Tayebi and El Kafhali (2025) proposed an enhanced XGBoost algorithm for detecting CCF, they tuned hyperparameters using Bayesian optimization (BO). Compared to traditional models, optimized XGBoost achieved higher accuracy, precision, and AUC. These findings suggest that traditional classifiers benefit substantially from the inclusion of boosting tree models in CCF detection.

Boosting models seem to also enhance deep neural networks (DNNs) performance in CCF detection. Gupta et al. (2022) proposed a hybrid model for CCF detection using LR, multilayer perceptron (MLP), and XGBoost. Results show the proposed hybrid ensemble model outperformed all standalone models, highlighting the strength of combining boosting models with DNNs. Mim et al. (2024) proposed a soft voting ensemble approach to improve CCF detection, they first tested eleven ML classifiers, among individual classifiers, XGBoost delivered the strongest recall (0.94) with the lowest false negative rate while MLP achieved the high-

Table 2.1: Recent research contributions on credit card fraud detection, summarizing models, class balancing strategies, and evaluation metrics.

Study	Model(s)	Class Balancing	Evaluation Metrics
Han and Joe (2025)	Ensemble (Light-GBM/XGBoost/CatBoost + SWA)	Data-level	ROC-AUC, PR, F1
Tayebi and El Kafhali (2025)	XGBoost (BO)	Data-level	ROC-AUC, F1
Wang et al. (2025)	TH-GCL	Algorithm-level	PR-AUC, ROC-AUC, F1
Mim et al. (2024)	Ensemble (XGBoost, RF, MLP)	Data-level	ROC-AUC, F1
Zhao et al. (2024)	CB-CHL-LightGBM, OS-CHL-LightGBM	Both	ROC-AUC, F2, MCC
Prabha and Priscilla (2023)	AE-XGBoost	Algorithm-level	ROC-AUC, F1, MCC, G-mean
Islam et al. (2023)	Stacked ensemble + XGBoost meta-learner	Algorithm-level	ROC-AUC, F1, MCC
Leevy et al. (2023)	CatBoost, XGBoost	None	ROC-AUC, PR-AUC
Ghaleb et al. (2023)	ESMOTE-GAN	Data-level	F1
Malik et al. (2022)	XGBoost, LightGBM	Both	F2
Gupta et al. (2022)	LR + XGBoost + MLP	Data-level	F1
Hashemi et al. (2022)	LightGBM, XGBoost, CatBoost (majority voting)	Algorithm-level	ROC-AUC, F1, MCC
Nguyen et al. (2022)	CatBoost + DNN	Data-level	ROC-AUC
Nti and Somanathan (2022)	RF-XGBoost	Data-level	ROC-AUC, F1
Tayebi and El Kafhali (2022)	DE-XGBoost	Data-level	F1
Ileberi et al. (2021)	AdaBoost + XGBoost	Data-level	ROC-AUC, MCC
Taha and Malebary (2020)	OLightGBM	None	ROC-AUC, F1

est AUROC (0.98). The best overall performer was the ensemble-based soft-voting classifier combining XGBoost, MLP, and KNN. These studies indicate the role of boosting models in enhancing DNNs performance in CCF detection.

Boosting models have been applied successfully as a standalone in CCF detection. A framework was proposed by (Tayebi and El Kafhali, 2022) using XGBoost and differential evolution (DE) for hyperparameter optimization. Results were tested on two real-world datasets, XGBoost with DE optimization outperformed all baseline models (e.g., RF, KNN, LR), achieving higher scores on several metrics including F-measure. Ghaleb et al. (2023) developed a CCF detection model that integrated advanced data augmentation with ensemble learning. They proposed ESMOTE-GAN technique to balance their data and tested several classifiers (KNN, ANN, SVM, LR, RF, and XGBoost), and found that tree-based models proved most effective with RF achieving an AUC of 92.9% while XGBoost closely followed with 92.8%, both significantly outperforming linear and neural models. Another study by Jemai et al. (2024) tested the effectiveness of ensemble learning methods for CCF detection using real-world and synthetic datasets recruiting Naive Bayes (NB), RF, and XGBoost. Results showed that NB consistently underperformed, while XGBoost achieved the strongest results across metrics. Moreover, models performed better on real dataset compared to synthetic. Overall, the findings highlight the robustness of boosting models in CCF detection and the superiority of using real dataset compared to synthetic.

A few studies adopted CatBoost in CCF detection (Han and Joe, 2025; Hashemi et al., 2022; Leevy et al., 2023; Nguyen et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2024). A study by Leevy et al. (2023) compared binary classifiers including CatBoost, XGBoost, and RF, and one-class classifiers including SVM and One-Class Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) on IEEE-CIS dataset. Their results showed that CatBoost achieved the highest PR-AUC (0.86) outperforming other models including XGBoost. Similarly, Han and Joe (2025) proposed a fraud detection framework. They used LightGBM, XGBoost, and CatBoost as baselines and enhanced their performance using voting, stacking, and stochastic weight averaging (SWA). Among these individual models, CatBoost achieved the highest ROC-AUC (0.991), while the stacked ensemble with SWA further improved results (ROC-AUC 0.997). Furthermore, Nguyen et al. (2022) proposed a hybrid model utilizing CatBoost and DNNs, where they separated old and new users, and applied CatBoost for known users and DNNs for unknown. CatBoost achieved higher score on ROC-AUC (0.97) compared to DNN model (0.84). While both models were complementary to each other in their performance. These findings highlight CatBoost's significant role in CCF tabular data.

Overall, boosting tree ensembles proved to be a strong baseline for CCF detection, either as a standalone classifier or when combined with traditional classifier or DNNs. Furthermore, XGBoost remains the most widely adopted model in CCF detection studies among tree-based models (Ghaleb et al., 2023; Gupta et al., 2022; Ileberi et al., 2021; Ileberi and Sun, 2024; Islam et al., 2023; Malik et al., 2022; Mim et al., 2024; Nti and Somanathan, 2022; Prabha and Priscilla, 2024, 2023; Tayebi and El Kafhali, 2022, 2025; Wang et al., 2025; AlSagri, 2025; Jemai et al., 2024; Xian, 2023), while CatBoost is less explored (Han and Joe, 2025; Hashemi et al., 2022; Leevy et al., 2023; Nguyen et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2024), especially as a standalone, despite

its strong ability to handle categorical features and class imbalance, which are present in CCF datasets.

2.3 Class Balancing Methods

The majority of CCF detection research relies on data-level class balancing methods (Han and Joe, 2025; Tayebi and El Kafhali, 2025; Ahmed et al., 2025; Mim et al., 2024; Almazroi and Ayub, 2023; Damanik and Liu, 2025; Ghaleb et al., 2023; Gupta et al., 2022; Nguyen et al., 2022; Nti and Somanathan, 2022; Ileberi et al., 2021; Tayebi and El Kafhali, 2022), with SMOTE being the most frequently applied. Nguyen et al. (2022) tackled class imbalance in the IEEE-CIS dataset using SMOTE and combined CatBoost and DNNs results for final predictions. They compared performance before and after applying SMOTE and found that while accuracy remained high, recall significantly improved. Similar findings were reported by (Gupta et al., 2022; Ileberi et al., 2021). Jemai et al. (2024) tested ROS, RUS, and SMOTE using three classifiers, NB, RF, and XGBoost, and showed SMOTE superior performance on real and synthetic datasets, where SMOTE achieved the highest recall and F1 score on all models. Other studies reached similar conclusions (Ahmed et al., 2025; Tayebi and El Kafhali, 2025; Gupta et al., 2025), showcasing the effectiveness of SMOTE (and its variants) as a data-level resampling method. Nonetheless, researchers warn against the risk of overfitting from using synthetic data and suggest combining it with other robust balancing techniques (Almazroi and Ayub, 2023).

Prior studies found that no sampling at all achieved better results compared to using data-level methods. Alarfaj et al. (2022) applied undersampling for balancing CCF dataset using a 14-layer CNN model and compared the results before and after balancing. Although both approaches performed well, the 14-layer CNN model performed better without resampling. The authors attributed this to reduced generalization caused by undersampling, which discards valid non-fraud samples.

Research points towards the disadvantages of employing data-level resampling methods, such as distorting data distribution, introducing noise leading to increased risk of overfitting, and loss of relevant information (He and Garcia, 2009; Kim and Song, 2025; Prabha and Priscilla, 2024). Due to drawbacks of applying data-level methods studies leverage it with algorithm-level methods. Malik et al. (2022) addressed class imbalance in CCF detection by integrating sampling techniques with CSL on the IEEE-CIS dataset. They tested different data-level methods and found SMOTE-ENN to be top-performer. However, they found that combining SMOTE-ENN with CSL significantly boosted the performance across all models. Demonstrating that combining data-level and algorithm-level (CSL) strategies is more effective for imbalanced fraud

detection. Comparable findings were reported by (Makki et al., 2019). These studies indicate the importance of algorithm-level role in class imbalance.

While less common than data-level methods, algorithm-level balancing techniques have been applied independently in CCF detection. Priscilla and Prabha (2021) relied on class weights in XGBoost for class imbalance, they applied a two-phase feature selection framework, achieving an improved ROC-AUC and reduced false negatives. Similarly, Hashemi et al. (2022) avoided using any data-level class imbalance methods due to false positives risk and relied on class-weight tuning within LR, XGBoost, LightGBM, CatBoost, and DNNs, using BO to tune the weights, they report model improvement across several metrics. Consistent findings on IEEE-CIS dataset were observed by (Wang et al., 2025). These studies show that algorithm-level methods can be effective on their own to handle extreme imbalance in CCF detection especially when combined with robust feature selection and hyperparameter optimization techniques.

Overall, prior studies show that algorithm-level class balancing can achieve strong performance independently and when combined with data-level. The literature also highlights the risks of data-level resampling, including potential overfitting and information loss. Despite this, algorithm-level methods are less commonly incorporated in CCF detection.

2.4 The Evaluation Metrics

Appropriate evaluation metrics in imbalanced data are necessary to reflect minority-class performance. For instance, accuracy alone can be misleading to rely on when faced with severe class imbalance (Bekkar et al., 2013; Hossin and Sulaiman, 2015), because it counts all correct predictions equally regardless of their class weights (He and Garcia, 2009). For instance, if 99% of the samples belong to the majority class and only 1% belongs to the minority class, a model that predicts only the majority and completely misses the minority can still achieve a 99% accuracy, creating a misleading impression of a strong performance.

A frequently used metric in CCF detection is the ROC-AUC, which measures how well a model separates positive cases (fraud) from negative cases (non-fraud) across all thresholds using both true positive rate (TPR) and the false positive rate (FPR)(Bekkar et al., 2013). The false positive rate is defined as:

$$\text{FPR} = \frac{FP}{FP + TN}$$

where FP and TN denote false positives and true negatives respectively. When severe class imbalance is present, the number of non-fraudulent transactions (i.e., TN) is very large. As a result, even with substantial increase in false positives, FPR remains small, falsely indicating a

low false positive rate. Since ROC-AUC is computed as the area under the TPR–FPR curve, this compression of the FPR axis inflates the ROC-AUC score (Davis and Goadrich, 2006), therefore, masking poor minority-class performance and giving optimistic results.

Similar to ROC-AUC, the PR-AUC is calculated across all thresholds and incorporates TPR, but replaces FPR with precision (Bekkar et al., 2013), defined as:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

where TP denotes true positives. Unlike FPR, precision depends only on the positive cases while ignoring the large number of negative cases. Therefore, increases in false positives directly reduce precision, preventing metric inflation and making PR-AUC more sensitive to minority-class errors and more suitable for highly imbalanced datasets.

Many studies recommend using PR-AUC and warn against relying on ROC-AUC. (Makki et al., 2019) argues that while ROC curves are standard, they can be misleading under extreme class imbalance because FPR can appear low simply due to the overwhelming number of negatives, they highlight that PR-AUC is more sensitive to imbalance. Similar arguments are made by other researchers (Hashemi et al., 2022; Leevy et al., 2023; Alamri and Ykhlef, 2024).

Despite this, a lot of studies in CCF detection rely on ROC-AUC and do not report PR-AUC (Almaraz-Rivera et al., 2025; Ahmed et al., 2025; Gupta et al., 2025; Ghaleb et al., 2023; Ileberi et al., 2021; Hashemi et al., 2022; Tayebi and El Kafhali, 2022; Nguyen et al., 2022; Nti and Somanathan, 2022; AlSagri, 2025; Iscan et al., 2023; Islam et al., 2023; Taha and Malebary, 2020; Zhao et al., 2024; Olowookere and Adewale, 2020; Malik et al., 2022; Mim et al., 2024; Prabha and Priscilla, 2023, 2024; Tayebi and El Kafhali, 2025). While the majority of these studies include precision, recall, and F1, which are helpful metrics in understanding how many frauds are caught (recall) (Sokolova and Lapalme, 2009), how many flagged frauds are real (precision) (Sokolova and Lapalme, 2009), and the balance between both (F1)(Bekkar et al., 2013), they reflect the model performance at a specific threshold point (Bekkar et al., 2013), rather than across the entire precision–recall trade-off space as represented by the PR-AUC metric (Saito and Rehmsmeier, 2015). So, PR-AUC shows how well the model performs across all possible cutoffs, as opposed to reflecting performance at a single cutoff, which might look good at one but perform poorly at another.

2.5 Summary and Research Gaps

Most studies in CCF detection applied XGBoost, while CatBoost’s adoption remains limited despite its ability to reduce prediction shift and overfitting via ordered boosting (Chen and Han, 2021), and its ability to mitigate target leakage through native categorical handling (Suguna et al., 2025). Furthermore, only a few CatBoost-based studies utilize algorithm-level imbalance handling (Hashemi et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2024), which can address class imbalance without altering the data distribution (Kim and Song, 2025), thereby reducing the risk of overfitting and information loss, commonly associated with data-level balancing methods (Spelman and Porkodi, 2018; Kim and Song, 2025). Last but not least, limited CatBoost-based studies reported PR-AUC (Leevy et al., 2023), even though it provides a more informative assessment under extreme class imbalance (Saito and Rehmsmeier, 2015). Consequently, the interaction between ordered CatBoost, algorithm-level class balance approaches, and PR-AUC evaluation remains underexplored. Moreover, a consistent comparative evaluation between CatBoost and widely applied models such as XGBoost and LightGBM is lacking, limiting clarity on CatBoost’s relative performance in CCF detection under comparable experimental and evaluation settings.

Hence, this study aims to address these gaps by comparing CatBoost with XGBoost and LightGBM using PR-AUC on the IEEE-CIS dataset before and after applying class imbalance techniques. The study further examines how the choice of evaluation metric (PR-AUC versus ROC-AUC) influences the interpretation of model performance under severe class imbalance, and evaluates whether algorithm-level imbalance methods (CSL) improve PR-AUC model performance relative to data-level methods (SMOTE, RUS, ROS).

3 Methodology

3.1 Datasets

The study used the publicly available IEEE-CIS Fraud Detection (2019) dataset (IEEE Computational Intelligence Society and Vesta Corporation, 2019). It contains anonymized data with 433 features (49 categorical) and 590,540 observations, including a binary fraud label. Fraud cases comprise 3.5% of the data (Fig. 3.1); feature details are summarized in Table 3.1, with selected feature distributions shown in Appendix B.

Figure 3.1: Class distribution of the IEEE-CIS dataset, showing severe class imbalance (3.5% fraud).

Additional datasets were utilized including the European Credit Card Fraud (ULB) (MLG ULB, 2013) and the Synthetic Financial Datasets for Fraud Detection (PaySim) (Lopez-Rojas et al., 2016). These datasets were used solely to examine whether the relative performance trends observed in the primary dataset (IEEE-CIS) remain consistent under different conditions, in-

Table 3.1: Summary of IEEE-CIS fraud detection dataset features, including feature groups, descriptions, and data types.

Feature	Description	Type
TransactionID	unique identifier	ID
isFraud	binary target	categorical
TransactionDT	time index	numerical
TransactionAmt	transaction amount	numerical
ProductCD	product code	categorical
card1-card6	card information	categorical
addr1-addr2	address	categorical
dist1-dist2	distance	numerical
P_emaildomain	purchaser email	categorical
R_emaildomain	recipient email	categorical
C1-C14	count features	numerical
D1-D15	time features	numerical
M1-M9	match indicators	categorical
V1-V339	engineered features	numerical
DeviceType	device type	categorical
DeviceInfo	device information	categorical
id_01-id_11	identification data	numerical
id_12-id_38	identification data	categorical

cluding varying class imbalance ratios, dataset sizes, and real versus synthetic data. Accordingly, only class balancing techniques (ROS, RUS, SMOTE, CSL) were applied to them without further feature engineering, feature selection, or hyperparameter tuning. Table 3.2 compares key characteristics of the datasets used in this study.

Table 3.2: Summary characteristics of the ULB and PaySim datasets, including dataset size, fraud rate, and data source (real vs. synthetic).

Dataset	Fraud Rate	Size	Source
IEEE-CIS	3.5%	590,000	Real
ULB	0.172%	284,807	Real
PaySim	0.13%	6.3 million	Synthetic

3.2 Data Cleaning

Data cleaning included correcting data types, dropping duplicates, removing features with over 99% missing values, removing the identifier column ‘TransactionID’.

IEEE-CIS is a real-world dataset containing a high volume of missing values, roughly 45%, Figure 3.2 illustrates how many features fall into different missing-value percentage ranges. In

real-world datasets, missingness may not always be completely at random (Little and Rubin, 2019), meaning that missingness may carry meaningful patterns.

Figure 3.2: Distribution of features by missing-value percentage, showing the number of features falling within each missingness range.

Standard missing value handling such as deletion or imputation can lead to biased inference. For instance, dropping missing values can remove potentially informative patterns, while mean/median imputation can dilute these patterns and mask true distributions (Little and Rubin, 2019; Saar-Tsechansky and Provost, 2007). Moreover, when the proportion of missing data increases, methods such as deletion or simple imputation can lead to greater bias regardless whether the data is missing at random or not (Horton and Kleinman, 2007).

These challenges call for careful handling of missing values in real-world datasets. Prior work on IEEE-CIS used mean/median and mode imputation (e.g., Almazroi and Ayub (2023)) or completely dropped missing values (e.g., Prabha and Priscilla (2023)). Increasing the risk of information loss and masking the real distribution, which may degrade model performance.

One solution to these challenges is to use arbitrary unique values, they preserve the information about missingness without blending it with real values or completely dropping it, allowing the model to learn from the absence of data (Saar-Tsechansky and Provost, 2007).

Tree-based models (LightGBM, XGBoost, CatBoost) can handle missing values natively and efficiently without the need for imputation or deletion (Rusdah and Murfi, 2020). In XGBoost, missingness is treated as part of the split decision. For instance, if a feature contains missing values, XGBoost tests two options for that split, sending left or right, and the option with higher loss reduction is picked (Chen, 2016). This direction becomes the default split direction for missing values at each tree node. This allows the model to route missing values without explicit

imputation or deletion (Chen, 2016). And CatBoost follows a similar logic to XGBoost, in that split decision can be influenced by missing values. More explicitly, missing values that appear in numeric features are handled during quantization by assigning them extreme bins (Min or Max) or completely not allowing them (CatBoost Developers, 2024). Within CatBoost’s learning framework (Prokhorenkova et al., 2018), if missingness correlates with the target, the split gain captures this signal and contributes to prediction, making missingness informative. Here, missing values were able to influence split decisions without the need for dropping or imputing. Missing values that appear in categorical features are treated as just another category and go through the same steps as other categories (e.g., target statistics, ordered encoding) (CatBoost Developers, 2024). Thus, missing categories receive their own learned statistics and can be predictive. In short, both XGBoost and CatBoost split decisions can be influenced by missing values, preserving potential informative missing-value patterns that the models can learn from.

Therefore, in the current study missing values were left as NaNs, the only time they were imputed was when applying SMOTE. SMOTE accepts numeric inputs only (Chawla et al., 2002), therefore, label encoding was used for all models, and label encoding requires missing values to be handled. Therefore, missing values were imputed using a sentinel value (-9999) for numerical features and ‘Missing’ for categorical features, a common approach in CCF detection (e.g., Menezes and Raimir Filho (2025); Shaohui et al. (2021); Chen and Han (2021)).

3.3 Feature Engineering

Feature engineering was conducted using a forward, cross-validated (CV) approach, adding features iteratively and retaining only those that improved model performance on PR-AUC. The process was done separately for each model and included the following categories:

- Missingness-based features created at both row and group level. For each row and group the number and ratio of missing values were calculated. Groups were created based on their attributes (e.g., card, address, email etc.). Binary missing flags were created for selected features to indicate whether a value was missing (1) or present (0).
- Time-based features extracted from transaction timestamp included duration (hours and days), cyclical time representations (e.g., minute, hour, weekday) encoded as sine and cosine, and elapsed time since the first transaction.
- Features derived from transaction amount such as split feature (e.g., cents, dollars) and natural logarithm of the transaction amount.
- Split features from ID columns (e.g., id_30, id_31, id_33, id_34).

- Email-based features including parent domain, suffix, and top-level domain.
- Device information derived features including company (e.g., Apple, Huawei), operating system (e.g., OS, Android), and binary flags whether mobile or browser-based.
- Frequency encoding of features with high cardinality and low missing values.
- Unique identifier (UID) created by combining card1, addr1, and a time-based component (TransactionDT – D1). This UID construction is inspired by Kaggle IEEE-CIS Fraud Detection competition, where similar user-level identifiers were created.¹ Related IEEE-CIS studies have modeled user behavior by grouping transactions using card, device, email domain, and temporal information (Almaraz-Rivera et al., 2025). Moreover, it has been shown in literature that combining strong features, such as cards, addresses, and time, enables the model to capture user-level behavioral patterns, known to be effective in CCF detection (Dal Pozzolo et al., 2017).
- Frequency encoding to key categorical variables and their combinations (e.g., card2, email, card1–addr1).
- Group-based statistics (e.g., mean, std) of transaction amounts aggregated by key identifiers (e.g., card1, card2).

3.4 Feature Selection

Low-contribution features were identified using correlations (Spearman ρ 0.95), mutual information (MI), TreeSHAP values, permutation feature importance, information gain, and time-inconsistent features. Low ranking features were considered for removal based on PR-AUC CV results. This process was applied to each model individually.

3.5 Class Imbalance Approach

Class imbalance was addressed using four resampling techniques, ROS, RUS, SMOTE, and CSL. CSL was implemented using model-specific class weighting schemes (e.g., class weights, scale_pos_weight). Table 3.3 shows the parameter values selected for each model based on PR-AUC results. Baseline models refer to the models at default setup prior to feature engineering and hyperparameter tuning; while final models refer to settings obtained after feature engineering

¹Chris Deotte, Kaggle IEEE-CIS Fraud Detection competition notebooks, 2019.

and hyperparameter optimization. Table 3.4 presents the CSL parameter values for each model on the ULB and PaySim datasets.

Table 3.3: CSL parameters for LightGBM, XGBoost, and CatBoost on the IEEE-CIS dataset, showing baseline and final values.

Model	CSL parameter	Baseline	Final
LightGBM	scale_pos_weight	3	7
XGBoost	scale_pos_weight	3	10
CatBoost	class weight	1:3	1:3

Table 3.4: CSL parameters for LightGBM, XGBoost, and CatBoost on the ULB and PaySim datasets

Model	CSL parameter	ULB	PaySim
LightGBM	scale_pos_weight	1.5	1.3
XGBoost	scale_pos_weight	16	12
CatBoost	class weight	1:4	1:5

3.6 Hyperparameter Optimization

Hyperparameters were tuned using Optuna’s BO with Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) and pruning. Optuna was used initially to guide the hyperparameter search, after which selected parameters were further refined manually based on CV performance. Default hyperparameters yielded the best performance for XGBoost and CatBoost; therefore, only default settings were used. In contrast, LightGBM benefited from Optuna-based optimization, the selected hyperparameters are reported in Table 3.5.

Table 3.5: Optimized LightGBM hyperparameters selected using Optuna.

Hyperparameter	Selected Value
Number of boosting iterations	3000
Learning rate	0.02
Number of leaves	500
Minimum samples per leaf	400

3.7 Evaluation Metrics

The primary evaluation metric used to evaluate model performance is the PR-AUC, which measures the tradeoff between precision and recall across all possible thresholds focusing on

the minority class (Bekkar et al., 2013). Additional metrics are reported, including threshold-independent (ROC-AUC) and threshold-dependent metrics (e.g., accuracy, precision, recall, F1, and MCC). All threshold-dependent metrics were computed at the default decision threshold ($\tau = 0.5$) to ensure consistent reporting across models.

3.8 Model Architecture

Fraud patterns in transactional data evolve over time and require time order to prevent temporal leakage, where the model peeks at future fraud patterns (Dal Pozzolo et al., 2017), potentially leading to overly optimistic performance that may not generalize at deployment time. Moreover, in transactional data, multiple rows (e.g., card information, email domain, etc.) can belong to the same user or entity, the transactions that come from the same are highly correlated and should be handled together (Whitrow et al., 2009). If the data from the same entity appears in both training and evaluation sets (entity leakage), models may memorize entity-specific patterns, leading to overly optimistic performance and may fail at real-world deployment. GroupKFold ensures that all samples from the same entity appear in only one fold.

Training the data on previous months and strictly testing on future months prevents temporal leakage, while using GroupKFold ensures that the same entity does not leak into other folds, preventing entity leakage. Therefore, this study used a time-aware 5-fold GroupKFold cross-validation using transaction month as the grouping variable, ensuring that the model was trained on earlier months and evaluated only on future data, a common approach in CCF datasets (Nguyen et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2025).

Initially, the models (LightGBM, XGBoost, CatBoost) were trained with default hyperparameter settings, fixed random state (42), and early stopping set to 100 rounds, to compare their baseline performance using PR-AUC and ROC-AUC on primary (IEEE-CIS) and secondary (ULB and PaySim) datasets. Then class balancing methods including ROS, RUS, SMOTE, and CSL were applied to the models and their performance was evaluated across all datasets. The secondary datasets were used to assess consistency of performance rankings across models, and were therefore not used for model development. For primary dataset, each model was optimized individually following the mentioned feature engineering (Section 3.3), feature selection (Section 3.4), and hyperparameter tuning procedures (Section 3.6). Afterwards, class balancing methods were applied to the optimized models and their performance was compared. The proposed methodology workflow is shown in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Proposed machine learning pipeline for data preprocessing, feature engineering, class balancing, and Bayesian hyperparameter optimization.

3.9 Experimental Environment

Experiments were run on a local Apple MacBook (M4 Pro Chip, 12-core CPU, 24 GB unified memory) on macOS 15.6.1. Software stack: Python 3.15.5, CatBoost 1.2.8, XGBoost 3.0.3, LightGBM 4.6.0, scikit-learn 1.6.1, optuna 4.6.0. The full implementation, including data preprocessing, model training, and the FastAPI inference service, is available at: <https://github.com/FatimaQatami/credit-card-fraud>.

4 Results

4.1 Performance Results

LightGBM, XGBoost, and CatBoost were trained on the IEEE-CIS dataset at baseline. Table 4.1 shows the baseline comparison results. The Models were trained again after feature engineering (Section 3.3), feature selection (see Section 3.4), and hyperparameter tuning (Section 3.6) representing the final models shown in Table 4.4. Class balancing techniques (ROS, RUS, SMOTE, CSL) were applied at baseline and for the final models. Figure 4.7 summarizes the performance of the final models on the IEEE-CIS dataset under different class-balancing strategies. To ensure results robustness, the models were evaluated on additional datasets (ULB and PaySim) under the same class-balancing methods, without feature engineering, feature selection, or hyperparameter tuning, as shown in Table 4.2 and 4.3. Additional evaluation metrics (e.g., precision, recall, F1-score) are reported for all models in the Appendix A.

The three models were first compared under baseline settings on the IEEE-CIS. CatBoost with CSL achieved the highest PR-AUC score (0.6660), followed by LightGBM (0.6075) and XGBoost with CSL (0.6060), as shown in Table 4.1. The ranking remained consistent on final models, where CatBoost with CSL achieved best PR-AUC score (0.7523), followed by LightGBM (0.6798) and XGBoost with CSL (0.6701) (see Table 4.4). This pattern also held on the additional datasets, where CatBoost with CSL outperformed XGBoost and LightGBM on the ULB and PaySim datasets with PR-AUC scores of 0.8356 and 0.9237, respectively (see Tables 4.2 and 4.3). Notably, across all models, performance on the IEEE-CIS dataset was consistently lower than on ULB and PaySim.

On the IEEE-CIS, CSL consistently outperformed all data-level methods (SMOTE, ROS, RUS) when used with CatBoost and XGBoost, both an baseline and final settings. For example, CatBoost with CSL achieved PR-AUC scores of 0.6660 and 0.7564, and XGBoost with CSL achieved PR-AUC scores of 0.6060 and 0.6701, respectively (see Tables 4.1 and 4.4). These patterns were also observed on the ULB and PaySim datasets, where CSL outperformed all data-level methods when used with CatBoost and XGBoost (see Tables 4.2 and 4.3).

Figure 4.1: Precision–Recall curve for the final LightGBM model on the IEEE-CIS dataset.

Figure 4.2: ROC curve for the final LightGBM model on the IEEE-CIS dataset.

An exception was observed for LightGBM, where the highest PR-AUC on the IEEE-CIS dataset was achieved without applying any class-balancing method, at baseline (0.6075) and at final settings (0.6798) (see Tables 4.1 and 4.4). And on ULB and PaySim datasets SMOTE was the best class-balancing method, with PR-AUC scores of 0.7927 and 0.9080 respectively (see Tables 4.2 and 4.3).

Table 4.1: Baseline CV performance on the IEEE-CIS dataset (mean \pm standard deviation) across class-balancing methods.

Model	Method	PR-AUC	ROC-AUC	Accuracy ($\tau = 0.5$)
LightGBM	None	0.6075 \pm 0.08	0.9177 \pm 0.02	0.9755 \pm 0.002
	SMOTE	0.5069 \pm 0.07	0.8829 \pm 0.01	0.9707 \pm 0.001
	ROS	0.5861 \pm 0.07	0.9112 \pm 0.01	0.9338 \pm 0.004
	RUS	0.5626 \pm 0.09	0.9160 \pm 0.02	0.8800 \pm 0.01
	CSL	0.6047 \pm 0.07	0.9160 \pm 0.02	0.9738 \pm 0.002
XGBoost	None	0.5826 \pm 0.08	0.9103 \pm 0.01	0.9746 \pm 0.001
	SMOTE	0.5463 \pm 0.08	0.8925 \pm 0.01	0.9729 \pm 0.002
	ROS	0.5541 \pm 0.06	0.8811 \pm 0.01	0.9547 \pm 0.002
	RUS	0.5638 \pm 0.08	0.9158 \pm 0.02	0.8904 \pm 0.01
	CSL	0.6060 \pm 0.08	0.9093 \pm 0.01	0.9750 \pm 0.001
CatBoost	None	0.6619 \pm 0.07	0.9306 \pm 0.02	0.9782 \pm 0.002
	SMOTE	0.6121 \pm 0.06	0.9170 \pm 0.01	0.9762 \pm 0.003
	ROS	0.4504 \pm 0.04	0.8752 \pm 0.01	0.9475 \pm 0.03
	RUS	0.6101 \pm 0.07	0.9294 \pm 0.01	0.9113 \pm 0.01
	CSL	0.6660 \pm 0.07	0.9338 \pm 0.01	0.9769 \pm 0.002

Table 4.2: Baseline CV performance on the ULB dataset (mean \pm standard deviation) across class-balancing methods.

Model	Method	PR-AUC	ROC-AUC	Accuracy ($\tau = 0.5$)
LightGBM	None	0.7187 \pm 0.08	0.9049 \pm 0.05	0.9990 \pm 0.0003
	SMOTE	0.7927 \pm 0.05	0.9798 \pm 0.01	0.9984 \pm 0.0004
	ROS	0.7654 \pm 0.08	0.9693 \pm 0.06	0.9987 \pm 0.001
	RUS	0.7635 \pm 0.07	0.9818 \pm 0.01	0.9264 \pm 0.03
	CSL	0.7116 \pm 0.09	0.9073 \pm 0.05	0.9986 \pm 0.0002
XGBoost	None	0.7445 \pm 0.06	0.9378 \pm 0.03	0.9992 \pm 0.0001
	SMOTE	0.8232 \pm 0.06	0.9789 \pm 0.01	0.9993 \pm 0.0001
	ROS	0.8242 \pm 0.06	0.9789 \pm 0.01	0.9995 \pm 0.0001
	RUS	0.7518 \pm 0.08	0.9815 \pm 0.01	0.9620 \pm 0.01
	CSL	0.8324 \pm 0.07	0.9815 \pm 0.01	0.9995 \pm 0.0001
CatBoost	None	0.8293 \pm 0.06	0.9814 \pm 0.01	0.9995 \pm 0.0001
	SMOTE	0.8198 \pm 0.05	0.9782 \pm 0.01	0.9974 \pm 0.0003
	ROS	0.8147 \pm 0.05	0.9692 \pm 0.01	0.9992 \pm 0.0001
	RUS	0.7361 \pm 0.08	0.9774 \pm 0.01	0.9806 \pm 0.01
	CSL	0.8356 \pm 0.06	0.9818 \pm 0.01	0.9995 \pm 0.00004

4.2 Compute Time and Efficiency

Computational efficiency was measured by training time (wall-clock time) for the baseline models to ensure a fair comparison across models and datasets. Table 4.5 presents the results. A tradeoff between performance and compute time can be observed.

4.3 Explainable AI (XAI) Using TreeSHAP

SHAP feature importance analysis was conducted on top-performing model, the results are presented in Figure 4.8 and show the most influential features in detecting fraud and their direction, whether a feature value pushes the prediction toward fraud (positive SHAP value) or away from it (negative SHAP value). As shown, the strongest contributor to the model’s prediction is the UID-based feature, followed by temporal features (e.g., D1n), transaction amount, and selected categorical variables (e.g., C13, C1).

Table 4.3: Baseline CV performance on the PaySim dataset (mean \pm standard deviation) across class-balancing methods.

Model	Method	PR-AUC	ROC-AUC	Accuracy ($\tau = 0.5$)
LightGBM	None	0.6319 \pm 0.26	0.9720 \pm 0.01	0.9931 \pm 0.01
	SMOTE	0.9080 \pm 0.04	0.9984 \pm 0.002	0.9495 \pm 0.04
	ROS	0.8932 \pm 0.03	0.9973 \pm 0.004	0.9967 \pm 0.004
	RUS	0.8529 \pm 0.05	0.9988 \pm 0.002	0.9911 \pm 0.002
	CSL	0.7258 \pm 0.12	0.9666 \pm 0.02	0.9954 \pm 0.01
XGBoost	None	0.7160 \pm 0.31	0.9810 \pm 0.03	0.9982 \pm 0.003
	SMOTE	0.9123 \pm 0.03	0.9978 \pm 0.003	0.9481 \pm 0.04
	ROS	0.8787 \pm 0.03	0.9983 \pm 0.002	0.9975 \pm 0.004
	RUS	0.8760 \pm 0.03	0.9992 \pm 0.001	0.9883 \pm 0.004
	CSL	0.9166 \pm 0.03	0.9993 \pm 0.001	0.9996 \pm 0.0003
CatBoost	None	0.9175 \pm 0.03	0.9990 \pm 0.001	0.9992 \pm 0.001
	SMOTE	0.8733 \pm 0.06	0.9984 \pm 0.002	0.9678 \pm 0.03
	ROS	0.0329 \pm 0.04	0.8529 \pm 0.04	0.9986 \pm 0.001
	RUS	0.8835 \pm 0.03	0.9991 \pm 0.001	0.9883 \pm 0.004
	CSL	0.9237 \pm 0.03	0.9989 \pm 0.001	0.9989 \pm 0.001

Table 4.4: CV performance on the IEEE-CIS dataset after feature engineering and hyperparameter tuning (mean \pm standard deviation).

Model	Method	PR-AUC	ROC-AUC	Accuracy ($\tau = 0.5$)
LightGBM	None	0.6798 \pm 0.08	0.9346 \pm 0.02	0.9780 \pm 0.002
	SMOTE	0.6791 \pm 0.09	0.9466 \pm 0.01	0.9774 \pm 0.001
	ROS	0.6630 \pm 0.07	0.9056 \pm 0.02	0.9785 \pm 0.001
	RUS	0.6263 \pm 0.08	0.9366 \pm 0.02	0.8997 \pm 0.02
	CSL	0.6773 \pm 0.08	0.9295 \pm 0.02	0.9779 \pm 0.003
XGBoost	None	0.6227 \pm 0.07	0.9223 \pm 0.01	0.9763 \pm 0.002
	SMOTE	0.5898 \pm 0.09	0.9138 \pm 0.01	0.9744 \pm 0.001
	ROS	0.6631 \pm 0.07	0.9281 \pm 0.02	0.9770 \pm 0.003
	RUS	0.6009 \pm 0.07	0.9304 \pm 0.01	0.9069 \pm 0.01
	CSL	0.6701 \pm 0.07	0.9341 \pm 0.02	0.9788 \pm 0.001
CatBoost	None	0.7451 \pm 0.09	0.9562 \pm 0.02	0.9813 \pm 0.001
	SMOTE	0.6893 \pm 0.07	0.9480 \pm 0.01	0.9785 \pm 0.001
	ROS	0.6712 \pm 0.06	0.9419 \pm 0.02	0.9758 \pm 0.004
	RUS	0.6705 \pm 0.08	0.9332 \pm 0.02	0.9478 \pm 0.01
	CSL	0.7523 \pm 0.07	0.9605 \pm 0.01	0.9800 \pm 0.003

Table 4.5: Computational efficiency comparison based on baseline training time (seconds) for each model across datasets.

Model	IEEE-CIS	ULB	PaySim
LightGBM	4.05	1.02	6.82
XGBoost	11.12	0.81	148.31
CatBoost	342.28	5.91	947.81

Figure 4.3: Precision–Recall curve for the final XGBoost model on the IEEE-CIS dataset.

Figure 4.4: ROC curve for the final XGBoost model on the IEEE-CIS dataset.

Figure 4.5: Precision–Recall curve for the final CatBoost model on the IEEE-CIS dataset.

Figure 4.6: ROC curve for the final CatBoost model on the IEEE-CIS dataset.

Figure 4.7: PR-AUC of final models on IEEE-CIS under different class-balancing strategies.

Figure 4.8: SHAP beeswarm plot illustrating the distribution and direction of feature impacts on model performance.

5 Ablation Studies

Ablation experimental studies were conducted to evaluate the impact of data splitting strategies, categorical feature handling, and parameter selection on model performance

- Using `TimeSeriesSplit` led to performance drop across all models, with an approximately 3.5% decrease in PR-AUC. In contrast, `GroupKFold` time-aware split, training on earlier months and validating on later months, consistently improved performance. Table 5.1 reports the impact of replacing `GroupKFold` with `TimeSeriesSplit` on PR-AUC, ROC-AUC, and training runtime. The reason may be that while `TimeSeriesSplit` preserves time-order and prevents temporal leakage (Pedregosa et al., 2024b), essential for effective CCF detection (Dal Pozzolo et al., 2017), it does not necessarily prevent entity leakage, where data from the same entity appears in both training and evaluation sets. `GroupKFold`, enforces entity separation, ensuring all samples belonging to same entity appear in only one fold (Pedregosa et al., 2024a), preventing entity leakage between training and validation sets. Prior work showed that fraud patterns can evolve abruptly rather than smoothly over time to adapt to higher security measures (Dal Pozzolo et al., 2017). In such condition, `TimeSeriesSplit` can make learning challenging, because it enforces strict chronological boundary (Pedregosa et al., 2024b), limiting the model's exposure to emerging fraud patterns during training that may not evolve in a strictly linear manner.
- Applying label encoding for `LightGBM` and `XGBoost` resulted in performance degradation compared native categorical feature handling. `LightGBM` and `XGboost` PR-AUC score dropped by 0.034 and 0.020, respectively. This may be due to label encoding altering how categorical information is represented, while native categorical handling preserves more informative structure.
- Applying depthwise growth in `CatBoost` led to a decrease of 0.045 in PR-AUC and 0.015 in ROC-AUC. However, training runtime was reduced by 234.7 s (69%). Depthwise growth splits only the best leaf at a given depth, as opposed to `CatBoost`'s default symmetric growth which splits all leaves at that depth (CatBoost Developers, 2024). This makes depthwise faster since it is not splitting at each leaf, but can limit the model's ability to

capture complex patterns, leading to lower performance.

Table 5.1: Changes in performance (Δ PR-AUC, Δ ROC-AUC) and runtime relative to GroupK-Fold when using TimeSeriesSplit.

Model	Δ PR-AUC	Δ ROC-AUC	Runtime Reduction (%)
LightGBM	-0.0350	-0.0233	20% (-0.81 s)
XGBoost	-0.0358	-0.0232	27% (-3.05 s)
CatBoost	-0.0355	-0.0168	42% (-143.8 s)

6 Discussion

The study findings reveal that CatBoost tend to outperform XGBoost and LightGBM consistently at baseline and at final configurations, and regardless of the class balancing method applied on the IEEE-CIS dataset. The findings were consistent across the ULB and PaySim datasets and align with prior studies. Leevy et al. (2023) reported superior CatBoost performance over XGBoost on ULB, while Zhao et al. (2024) found CatBoost achieved higher ROC-AUC than LightGBM on the same dataset.

One possible explanation for these findings lies in how the models handle missing values. While CatBoost, XGBoost, and LightGBM allow NaNs during training and include them in split decisions without explicit need for imputation or deletion, their approaches differ. XGBoost and LightGBM primarily handle missing values by learning an optimal default direction during tree splits (Chen, 2016; Murthy and Kumar, 2025), while CatBoost goes further than split decisions and treat NaNs as distinct values, allowing the model to capture patterns associated with the missingness (CatBoost Developers, 2024; Murthy and Kumar, 2025). Given that IEEE-CIS dataset contains high volume of missing values (45%), the way they were handled likely had a substantial impact on model performance.

Another explanation relates to categorical features handling. All three models support native categorical handling, eliminating the need for external encoding (e.g., one-hot, label encoding) (Chen, 2016; Prokhorenkova et al., 2018; Hancock and Khoshgoftaar, 2021). However, these internal processes differ. Statistical encoding can introduce target leakage if future data are used (Prokhorenkova et al., 2018). While CatBoost uses statistical encoding, it enforces ordered boosting for encoding categories, where it does not look at future data, reducing target leakage and overfitting (Prokhorenkova et al., 2018). In contrast, XGBoost, converts categories to integer identifiers to perform split-based handling, without incorporating target-based statistics (XGBoost Developers, 2023), avoiding target leakage but potentially yielding less informative splits, because are not informed by label-dependent statistics. LightGBM orders categories using label-dependent statistics (e.g., mean target), enabling more informative splits but increasing the risk of target leakage and overfitting (LightGBM Developers, 2024).

Further contributing factor may stem from the difference in tree growth strategies. CatBoost grows symmetric (oblivious) trees by applying the same split at each depth across all nodes. In contrast, LightGBM and XGBoost employ classic asymmetric tree growth rather than symmetric structures (XGBoost Developers, 2023; LightGBM Developers, 2024). Oblivious trees have advantages over classic tree growth by offering a form of regularization, often leading to better generalization and reduced overfitting (CatBoost Developers, 2024). This aligns with the ablation study results, where changing CatBoost’s tree growth from symmetric to depthwise led to a performance drop (see Section 5).

Another finding is that algorithm-level class balancing method (CSL), seem to help model performance over data-level methods when evaluated on both PR-AUC and ROC-AUC. This improvement may be attributed to CSL, which help the way the model learn by modifying the loss function so that errors on the minority class are penalized more heavily (He and Garcia, 2009; Kim and Song, 2025). In contrast, data-level methods (e.g., SMOTE, ROS, RUS) alter the data distribution directly to achieve class balance, which can introduce synthetic noise, increase overfitting, or lead to information loss (He and Garcia, 2009; Kim and Song, 2025), potentially limiting model performance. These findings align with Malik et al. (2022), who showed that CSL improved XGBoost and LightGBM performance relative to data-level methods.

All models consistently had lower performance on the IEEE-CIS dataset. IEEE-CIS is high-dimensional and noisy, with over 400 features, whereas ULB contains 30 PCA-transformed features. PaySim includes 11 synthetic features, providing cleaner and more structured data (Alamri and Ykhlef, 2024).

An additional observation is that class balancing methods behaved consistently for CatBoost and XGBoost across datasets, where CSL was the top performer for both models across the three datasets. However, LightGBM behavior was less consistent across datasets. On the IEEE-CIS dataset, LightGBM performed best without class balancing, while on the ULB and PaySim datasets SMOTE yielded superior results. This may suggest that LightGBM is more sensitive to dataset structures, where it benefits from resampling methods in smoother or lower-dimensional settings (e.g., ULB and PaySim), while benefits more from robust feature engineering and tuning in complex datasets (e.g., IEEE-CIS). Indeed, some studies focused on feature engineering and evaluation metrics rather than explicit class balancing in CCF detection (Almaraz-Rivera et al., 2025).

Consistent with prior work on imbalanced classification ((Damanik and Liu, 2025; Leevy et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2025)), ROC-AUC values were consistently higher than PR-AUC across all models. The observed lower PR-AUC values compared to ROC-AUC are expected under severe class imbalance, as PR-AUC is more sensitive to changes in minority-class performance,

whereas ROC-AUC can remain optimistic (Davis and Goadrich, 2006; Saito and Rehmsmeier, 2015). This further highlights the importance of reporting PR-AUC alongside ROC-AUC when evaluating fraud detection models in imbalanced settings.

Notably, CatBoost remained the top-performing model across all datasets and regardless of the dataset or the class-balancing method applied. Nonetheless, training time was significantly higher compared to LightGBM and XGBoost, consistent with findings reported in prior work (Suguna et al., 2025). In high-stakes domains such as banking, where missed fraud can result in significant financial loss, an improvement may justify an increase in training time.

TreeSHAP analysis was performed on the final top-performing model (CatBoost + CSL) and revealed that it was primarily driven by UID-based feature followed by C13, D1n, and TransactionAmt. This suggests that the model primarily relies on user-level behavioral patterns rather than individual transactions, which is well-established in literature (Almaraz-Rivera et al., 2025; Dal Pozzolo et al., 2017). In addition, higher transaction amount (TransactionAmt) and temporal feature (D1n) values tend to be associated with higher fraud risk. And for several categorical features (e.g., C13, C1, C14) both high and low values influence predictions reflecting non-linear relationship between these variables and fraud risk. Overall, the TreeSHAP analysis indicates that the model’s predictions are mainly driven by user-level behavioral features, with higher transaction amounts and certain temporal patterns increasing fraud risk.

6.1 Study Limitations and Future Direction

This study focused on a controlled comparative analysis of CatBoost with other boosting models in CCF detection. As a result, the emphasis was placed on consistency across models rather than exhaustive optimization. Further gains may be achievable through incorporating more advanced integrated frameworks. Further, CatBoost exhibited higher training time, which may limit its applicability in resource- or time-constrained settings. Future work could explore employing simplified CatBoost configurations during early experimentation (e.g., plain boosting, depthwise tree growth). Additionally, the study calculated threshold-dependent metrics (e.g., recall, precision) at a fixed default threshold ($\tau=0.5$), this may not be optimal for all performance objectives, future work could explore optimizing the decision threshold, such as maximizing for F2-score for higher minority-class sensitivity.

7 Conclusion

The current study compared CatBoost, XGBoost, and LightGBM on the IEEE-CIS CCF dataset, investigating data-level and algorithm-level methods for handling class imbalance, evaluated on PR-AUC. The results show that Catboost consistently outperformed XGBoost and LightGBM, and that algorithm-level class balancing method (CSL) is more effective than data-level for fraud detection. In particular, combining CatBoost with CSL provides a robust solution for fraud detection under severe class imbalance, with consistent findings across the ULB and PaySim datasets. Despite strong performance, CatBoost's higher training cost may limit applicability in resource-constrained settings, motivating exploration of more efficient configurations. Overall, this work provides controlled comparison between boosting algorithms and class balancing techniques, offering practical insight for advancing fraud detection research and practice.

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Appendix A

A Additional Results

Table A.1: Baseline CV performance on the IEEE-CIS dataset (mean \pm standard deviation) across class-balancing methods at $\tau = 0.5$.

Model	Method	Precision	Recall	F1	MCC
LightGBM	None	0.81 \pm 0.14	0.42 \pm 0.04	0.55 \pm 0.06	0.57 \pm 0.07
	SMOTE	0.67 \pm 0.15	0.39 \pm 0.02	0.49 \pm 0.05	0.49 \pm 0.06
	ROS	0.31 \pm 0.06	0.70 \pm 0.03	0.43 \pm 0.06	0.44 \pm 0.05
	RUS	0.20 \pm 0.05	0.79 \pm 0.03	0.32 \pm 0.06	0.36 \pm 0.05
	CSL	0.69 \pm 0.02	0.51 \pm 0.03	0.58 \pm 0.07	0.58 \pm 0.07
XGBoost	None	0.76 \pm 0.02	0.44 \pm 0.03	0.55 \pm 0.05	0.56 \pm 0.06
	SMOTE	0.73 \pm 0.17	0.41 \pm 0.03	0.52 \pm 0.06	0.53 \pm 0.07
	ROS	0.41 \pm 0.06	0.59 \pm 0.02	0.48 \pm 0.05	0.47 \pm 0.04
	RUS	0.22 \pm 0.05	0.78 \pm 0.03	0.34 \pm 0.06	0.38 \pm 0.05
	CSL	0.72 \pm 0.15	0.51 \pm 0.03	0.58 \pm 0.06	0.59 \pm 0.07
CatBoost	None	0.84 \pm 0.11	0.48 \pm 0.04	0.61 \pm 0.05	0.62 \pm 0.06
	SMOTE	0.79 \pm 0.11	0.46 \pm 0.04	0.58 \pm 0.05	0.59 \pm 0.06
	ROS	0.40 \pm 0.15	0.46 \pm 0.09	0.40 \pm 0.05	0.40 \pm 0.05
	RUS	0.26 \pm 0.05	0.77 \pm 0.03	0.38 \pm 0.06	0.41 \pm 0.05
	CSL	0.74 \pm 0.15	0.56 \pm 0.03	0.63 \pm 0.07	0.63 \pm 0.08

Table A.2: Baseline CV performance on the ULB dataset (mean \pm standard deviation) across class-balancing methods at $\tau = 0.5$.

Model	Method	Precision	Recall	F1	MCC
LightGBM	None	0.66 \pm 0.13	0.74 \pm 0.15	0.70 \pm 0.13	0.70 \pm 0.13
	SMOTE	0.52 \pm 0.02	0.85 \pm 0.04	0.64 \pm 0.03	0.66 \pm 0.03
	ROS	0.64 \pm 0.18	0.83 \pm 0.07	0.70 \pm 0.13	0.72 \pm 0.10
	RUS	0.03 \pm 0.01	0.94 \pm 0.02	0.05 \pm 0.03	0.14 \pm 0.04
	CSL	0.56 \pm 0.13	0.78 \pm 0.11	0.65 \pm 0.12	0.66 \pm 0.11
XGBoost	None	0.83 \pm 0.06	0.67 \pm 0.10	0.74 \pm 0.06	0.74 \pm 0.05
	SMOTE	0.77 \pm 0.10	0.83 \pm 0.05	0.80 \pm 0.06	0.80 \pm 0.06
	ROS	0.85 \pm 0.14	0.82 \pm 0.05	0.83 \pm 0.06	0.83 \pm 0.06
	RUS	0.04 \pm 0.02	0.92 \pm 0.04	0.04 \pm 0.08	0.19 \pm 0.05
	CSL	0.87 \pm 0.09	0.79 \pm 0.07	0.83 \pm 0.07	0.83 \pm 0.07
CatBoost	None	0.91 \pm 0.04	0.74 \pm 0.11	0.81 \pm 0.07	0.82 \pm 0.06
	SMOTE	0.51 \pm 0.20	0.85 \pm 0.06	0.61 \pm 0.20	0.64 \pm 0.15
	ROS	0.75 \pm 0.08	0.82 \pm 0.05	0.78 \pm 0.05	0.78 \pm 0.05
	RUS	0.09 \pm 0.05	0.89 \pm 0.03	0.15 \pm 0.08	0.26 \pm 0.07
	CSL	0.89 \pm 0.05	0.79 \pm 0.07	0.83 \pm 0.05	0.84 \pm 0.05

Table A.3: Baseline CV performance on the PaySim dataset (mean \pm standard deviation) across class-balancing methods at $\tau = 0.5$.

Model	Method	Precision	Recall	F1	MCC
LightGBM	None	0.58 \pm 0.31	0.82 \pm 0.06	0.62 \pm 0.30	0.65 \pm 0.24
	SMOTE	0.07 \pm 0.09	0.99 \pm 0.01	0.13 \pm 0.15	0.22 \pm 0.17
	ROS	0.44 \pm 0.25	0.74 \pm 0.07	0.55 \pm 0.21	0.61 \pm 0.16
	RUS	0.13 \pm 0.04	1.0 \pm 0.004	0.22 \pm 0.07	0.35 \pm 0.06
	CSL	0.61 \pm 0.31	0.82 \pm 0.04	0.65 \pm 0.28	0.67 \pm 0.23
XGBoost	None	0.72 \pm 0.30	0.80 \pm 0.08	0.71 \pm 0.23	0.73 \pm 0.19
	SMOTE	0.10 \pm 0.13	0.99 \pm 0.01	0.16 \pm 0.20	0.24 \pm 0.21
	ROS	0.62 \pm 0.30	0.85 \pm 0.09	0.67 \pm 0.21	0.70 \pm 0.16
	RUS	0.10 \pm 0.02	1.0 \pm 0.004	0.18 \pm 0.04	0.31 \pm 0.04
	CSL	0.92 \pm 0.11	0.79 \pm 0.06	0.84 \pm 0.04	0.85 \pm 0.04
CatBoost	None	0.78 \pm 0.24	0.84 \pm 0.10	0.78 \pm 0.013	0.80 \pm 0.11
	SMOTE	0.10 \pm 0.11	0.99 \pm 0.01	0.16 \pm 0.17	0.26 \pm 0.18
	ROS	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00
	RUS	0.10 \pm 0.03	1.0 \pm 0.004	0.18 \pm 0.05	0.31 \pm 0.05
	CSL	0.72 \pm 0.25	0.88 \pm 0.09	0.76 \pm 0.15	0.78 \pm 0.12

Table A.4: CV performance on the IEEE-CIS dataset after feature engineering and hyperparameter tuning (mean \pm standard deviation) at $\tau = 0.5$.

Model	Method	Precision	Recall	F1	MCC
LightGBM	None	0.86 \pm 0.02	0.46 \pm 0.03	0.60 \pm 0.05	0.62 \pm 0.06
	SMOTE	0.82 \pm 0.16	0.47 \pm 0.02	0.60 \pm 0.06	0.61 \pm 0.07
	ROS	0.80 \pm 0.13	0.53 \pm 0.03	0.64 \pm 0.06	0.64 \pm 0.07
	RUS	0.24 \pm 0.06	0.83 \pm 0.03	0.37 \pm 0.01	0.41 \pm 0.07
	CSL	0.77 \pm 0.14	0.55 \pm 0.02	0.64 \pm 0.06	0.64 \pm 0.07
XGBoost	None	0.78 \pm 0.13	0.48 \pm 0.03	0.59 \pm 0.05	0.60 \pm 0.06
	SMOTE	0.75 \pm 0.17	0.44 \pm 0.02	0.55 \pm 0.06	0.56 \pm 0.08
	ROS	0.74 \pm 0.15	0.57 \pm 0.02	0.63 \pm 0.08	0.63 \pm 0.08
	RUS	0.25 \pm 0.06	0.79 \pm 0.02	0.38 \pm 0.07	0.41 \pm 0.06
	CSL	0.82 \pm 0.14	0.53 \pm 0.02	0.64 \pm 0.06	0.64 \pm 0.07
CatBoost	None	0.86 \pm 0.13	0.56 \pm 0.0	0.68 \pm 0.07	0.69 \pm 0.07
	SMOTE	0.79 \pm 0.12	0.54 \pm 0.02	0.64 \pm 0.05	0.64 \pm 0.05
	ROS	0.94 \pm 0.02	0.35 \pm 0.04	0.50 \pm 0.04	0.56 \pm 0.03
	RUS	0.39 \pm 0.09	0.74 \pm 0.03	0.50 \pm 0.09	0.51 \pm 0.07
	CSL	0.76 \pm 0.14	0.65 \pm 0.02	0.69 \pm 0.08	0.69 \pm 0.08

Appendix B

B Feature Distributions of IEEE-CIS

Figure B.1: Distribution of ProductCD values (IEEE-CIS).

Figure B.2: Distribution of transaction amounts (TransactionAmt) in IEEE-CIS.

Figure B.3: Distribution of dist1 values (IEEE-CIS).

Figure B.4: Distribution of dist2 values (IEEE-CIS).

Figure B.5: Distribution of card4 (payment network: Visa, Mastercard, American Express, Discover) in IEEE-CIS.

Figure B.6: Distribution of card6 transaction types (debit vs. credit) in IEEE-CIS.

Figure B.7: Distribution of id_01 values in the IEEE-CIS dataset.

Figure B.8: Distribution of id_02 values in the IEEE-CIS dataset.

Figure B.9: Distribution of id_07 values in the IEEE-CIS dataset.

Figure B.10: Distribution of id_08 values in the IEEE-CIS dataset.

Figure B.11: Distribution of id_24 values in the IEEE-CIS dataset.

Figure B.12: Distribution of id_35 values in the IEEE-CIS dataset.

Figure B.13: Distribution of id_36 values in the IEEE-CIS dataset.

Figure B.14: Distribution of id_37 values in the IEEE-CIS dataset.

Figure B.15: Distribution of id_38 values in the IEEE-CIS dataset.